

D1.1: Open Data Management Plan

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Abstract

As part of the Task 1.3 – Data and knowledge management, this deliverable aims to create a Data Management Plan (DMP) able to describe the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated in the frame of the LaserWay project and is in-line with the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data Pilot initiative. Therefore, this deliverable intends to help project partners in making the research data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable to favour data and knowledge integration, as well as, to enable maximum access and re-use of the project data for societal and economic benefits.

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Symbols, abbreviations and acronyms

Symbols, abbreviations and acronyms	Description
CNC	Computer Numerical Control
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Policy
IP	Intellectual Property
WP	Work Package
FTO	Freedom To Operate
XML	Extensible Markup Language
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
FCA	Financial Conduct Authority
SEN	Sensitive documents
NGO	Non-Governmental Organizations
SCC	EU Standard Contractual Clauses
EEA	European Economic Area
DAGs	Data Availability Groups
CMOS	Complementary Metal–Oxide–Semiconductor
EU	European Union
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
REST API	Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface
CCO	Creative Commons
CERN	European Organization for Nuclear Research
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
FundRef	Open Funder Registry
OpenAIRE	European project supporting Open Science

1 Introduction

This report constitutes one of the main outcomes of the task 1.3 of WP1 where a Data Management Plan (DMP) for LaserWay project is defined in order to establish proper data management and data protection procedures, including GDPR compliance policies. The main objective is to support the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data Pilot initiative, to enable maximum access and re-use of the project data for societal and economic benefits.

1.1 To be implemented Scope and Objectives

This Deliverable 1.1 should be considered as a guideline for a proper and safe data management along the project execution, covering aspects such as the fulfilment of FAIR values (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable data management), along with any ethics and legal issues related to GDPR policies developed in Laserway project for the protection of personal data. This document describes the datasets that will be created, processed and shared within the project and how these data relate to the project objectives and the WP structure.

1.2 Relationship to Other Project Outcomes

The present document contemplates in detail all the data that will be produced and shared along the Laserway project. It has a clear relationship with the exploitation management activities defined in task 7.2 and task 8.2 and their corresponding outcomes (deliverable D7.3 and deliverable D8.2) and also with dissemination activities to be implemented in task 7.1 and 8.1 and the derived outcomes (deliverables D7.1 and D8.1) , where a protection strategy will be defined for all the generated knowledge, including the generated and shared data, and the access rights for result exploitation will be determined. This will ensure freedom to operate (FTO) of the results and propose FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) solutions for potential IPR conflicts.

1.3 Structure of the document

A brief description of the structure is described below:

Introduction: the introductory section of the deliverable.

Section 2 is the analysis of the Data Management Plan.

Section 3 is the description of the data sets per WP.

Section 4 outlines the FAIR principles and contributions to Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP).

2 LaserWay data management plan (LaserWay DMP)

Following the LaserWay DMP will be exposed, where data management life cycle for all the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by the project will be described. It includes data flows in the context of specific use cases, structured reports for the evaluation of the

process and information on: - the handling of research data during & after the end of the project - what data will be collected, processed and/or generated - which methodology & standards will be applied - whether data will be shared/made open access and - how data will be curated & preserved (including after the end of the project).

2.1 Data Lifecycle

In this point, the entire data lifecycle regarding the project is examined. The corresponding steps at which data will be created and acquired, processed and/or utilized during the execution of the project and afterwards are taken into account. Based on the typical Data Lifecycle diagram (see Figure 1), an analysis of the data lifecycle as well as the means to control, manage and report the related data of LaserWay project is performed. In each of the sections that follow, specific metrics for the data management and control have been included that will be considered as milestones in order to ensure the compliancy with the data management plan.

Figure 1: LaserWay Data Lifecycle

2.1.1 Data Collection & Acquisition

In this stage the data collection and/or acquisition within the LaserWay activities and demonstrations along with the project reports and other documents/spreadsheets are considered. This includes the creation of the data by each of the respective owner/partner

and the collection in a structured approach, appropriate format, and layout to enable their processing by the rest of the project components/modules. The specific assessment criteria in this phase are shown in the Table 1.

Performance measurement	Means of verification	Milestones
Format	Open languages and formats will be privileged in order to allow exchanges and increase the capacity to combine metadata	Universal File Format and XML
Availability and Readability	Whole package of data available avoiding any corruption; data accessible through partners website	100% integrity 100% accessibility
Ready to use	Data produced by each partner will be of direct usefulness to the rest of the Consortium for the development of the project; the project's outputs will be helpful for a broad audience including researchers, scientific organizations, technical professional magazines, large industries, and SMEs	100% usable by intended beneficiary/ies
Consistency and Completeness	Data are consistent and complete for the intended purpose	Including 100% of information for the intended purpose
Relation	Data following a precise relation to their purpose	100% purpose precision

Table 1: LaserWay specific assessment criteria for data collection and acquisition

2.1.2 Data Processing & Analysis

This stage is related to the actual data processing by the various data processors that are the project partners who will have access to the data for management following the project needs and outcomes. The processing of the data in a concise way by the suitable partners needs to be guaranteed in order to fulfil the LaserWay project needs. This stage includes all steps towards data verification, organization, transformation, integration and extraction for the intended use. The data Analysis is the next stage and is tightly connected with the data processing previously described. It includes all the actions/methodology executed on the actual data that describe existing facts, identify outlines, develop data clarifications etc. Specific evaluation criteria at this stage are described in Table 2.

Performance measurement	Means of verification	Milestones
Data logic	Data can be and are processed following a concise logic and approach	New and processed data follow precise data logic
Organization and Utility	Suitable content organization of data under processing	100% organized data
Validation	Ensuring that the data under processing are correct and relevant	100% validated and relevant data
Aggregation	Whenever multiple data need to be aggregated ensure that this is done in a concise approach	100% aggregate-able data
Transformation	Transformation of data to the proper format(s) for processing	Capability of data for transformation (if needed)
Calibration	Calibration of data for their intended purpose	Data properly calibrated

Table 2: LaserWay evaluation criteria for data processing and analysis

2.1.3 Data Usage & Security

With respect to the data utility/usage, the management of the data is based on a level system where the data is categorized depending on its of direct usefulness for the rest of the Consortium (internal data associated to Project management, type SEN-sensitive documents, report versions, internal recordings of review meetings,...) for the development of the project, or the outputs considered to be helpful for a broad audience including researchers, scientific organizations, technical professional magazines, large industries, and SMEs in the fields of machine tools, photonics, etc., as well as for regulatory agencies (FCA.), policy and government decision makers, NGOs, and general public (additionally, LaserWay’s derivative data might influence and contribute to the development of future, approved, or on-going projects in the same topic of Horizon Europe). This stage is closely linked to the following one (Data Archiving & Disposal) as far as metadata is related to ensure data search-ability (as another feature of the FAIR data treatment, see FAIR Data Management). Specific evaluation criteria at this stage are shown in Table 3.

Performance measurement	Means of verification	Milestones
Data with direct usefulness for the Consortium. Data Security	Data stored in a suitable server	100% Consortium internal data stored in Sharepoint*

Open-source Data. To be published in different dissemination activities along the project.	Data stored in a suitable server	100% Data stored in Zenodo **
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Table 3: LaserWay evaluation criteria for data usage and security

* **Sharepoint:** Microsoft offers customers the EU Standard Contractual Clauses (SCC) that provides specific guarantees around transfers of personal data for in-scope services. The EU model Clauses are used in agreements between service providers (such as Microsoft) and their customers to ensure that any personal data leaving the European Economic Area (EEA) will be transferred in compliance with the GDPR.

SharePoint 365, a multi-tenant hyperscale cloud platform and an integrated experience of apps and services available to customers in several regions worldwide. Office 365 services enable customers to specify the region where their customer data is located. Microsoft may replicate customer data to other regions within the same geographic area for data resiliency, but Microsoft will not replicate customer data outside the chosen geographic area. One of the challenging aspects of running a large-scale cloud service is how to handle data corruption, given the large volume of data and independent systems. Data corruption can be used by:

- Application or infrastructure bugs, corrupting some or all of the application state.
- Hardware issues that result in lost data or an inability to read data.
- Human operational errors.
- Malicious hackers and disgruntled employees.
- Incidents in external services that result in some loss of data.

Because greater resiliency in data integrity means fewer data corruption incidents, Microsoft has built into Microsoft 365 protection mechanisms to prevent corruption from happening, as well as systems and processes that enable data-recovery if it does. Checks and processes exist within the various stages of the engineering release process to increase resiliency against data corruption, including:

- System design
- Code organization and structure
- Code review
- Unit tests, integration tests, and system tests
- Trip wires tests/gates

Within M365 production environments, peer replication between datacentres ensures that there are always multiple live copies of any data. Standard images and scripts are used to recover lost servers, and replicated data is used to restore customer data. In Exchange Online, every mailbox is hosted in Data Availability Groups (DAGs) and replicated to geographically separate datacentres within the same region. Each mailbox database has four copies distributed across datacentres within the DAG: one active copy, two up-to-date copy, and one 7-day lagged copy used in the rare event of catastrophic logical corruption. For SharePoint and OneDrive, files are written simultaneously to a primary and secondary datacentre region. Multiple types of checksums are stored in metadata in a separate location than the corresponding files and are used to ensure data integrity through all stages of the data lifecycle.

** **Zenodo:** To ensure data security, archiving and recovery, data files and metadata in Zenodo ([Search Extremely High-Speed Laser Processes For Sustainable And Flexible Manufacturing \(LaserWay\) \(zenodo.org\)](https://www.zenodo.org)) are backed up nightly and replicated into multiple copies in the online system. The official data centre resides in Geneva, while the centre for the copies/replicas is in Budapest.

2.1.4 Data Archiving & Disposal

The storage and archiving stages are also very critical as they relate to the data access, sharing, storage, archiving (including search capabilities), disposal and the secondary use of data. Once again, a data agreement would define the context under which the re-usage of data will be appropriately carried out by the interested actors. Important metrics here include the updated status of the data so that no later versions exist (unless is clearly indicated). Actions to ensure accidental data losses, corruption and unauthorized access should be also included. Data storage and archiving is also strongly linked to data re-usability that is also within the scope of the FAIR data management. Specific evaluation criteria at this stage are shown in Table 4.

Performance measurement	Means of verification	Milestones
Up to date	Ensuring that the stored data are up to date for the specific purpose and no later version exists	100% updated
Meta data	Existence of meta data in stored files	Relevant metadata have been included into the archive per data set
Security	Data stored in a suitable server with strong back up capabilities.	100% Data stored in Zenodo **
Bandwidth	Control of server bandwidth	Effective storage server bandwidth > 2 MBPS
Expiration	Properly setting expiration dates for all data after which the data will be deleted	Expiration date noted

Table 4: LaserWay evaluation criteria for data archiving and disposal

2.2 Data repositories and management

According with the above mentioned and for a comprehensible and long-term functional data management plan, it is required to analyse the origin of the data generated throughout the course of the project and their dissemination level which, except the SE degree, indicates for whom these data might be interesting, in order to identify the party that is responsible for their management, and appropriate repositories to host them (see Figure 2).

Data levels

Figure 2: LaserWay Data Flow

3 Data description

This section outlines the data produced or processed at each WP and elaborates a number of factors for each of the involved data objects. Each WP’s introductory subsection addresses the intended purpose of use of the provided data from the Data Owner’s perspective and relates them to the LaserWay’s objectives while the table structure below elaborates for each data element, the following vital information:

- Short description of data content and type
- Data origin/source (where the data come from)
- Data format - Confidentiality level (Public, Project Consortium, Data Processor(s), Research Purpose)
- Processing/Usage preconditions (restrictions).

By processing the data information from each WP, the establishment of an overview of the anticipated data types, formats, and size, as derived by the respective work package, is now feasible and summarized. Based on each WP input, it is foreseen that the total generated data will not exceed the size 4 TB.

3.1 WP1 LaserWay - Management

As this work package focuses on the project management, no existing scientific data will be particularly reused. However, in the scope of the data and knowledge management task (Task 1.3), the Horizon Europe guidelines and other external information sources will serve as the reference to formulate the DMP (Table 5).

Data Description	Data Origin / Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
Economic data	Partners	.docx, .xlsx	Project Consortium	Only for involved partners
Personal data	Partners	.docx, .pdf	Project Consortium	Only for involved partners
Risk management documents	Partners	.docx, .pdf	Project Consortium.	Only for involved partners
Deliverables	Partners	.docx, .pdf	Project Consortium	N/A
Project data	Partners	.docx, .pdf, .ppt, .xlsx	Project Consortium.	Only for involved partners

Table 5: LaserWay WP1 Data Mapping

3.2 WP2 WayHARDER requirements

The second WP of LaserWay is dedicated to the requirements definition based on the user-cases needs. The main input would be the data generated from material suppliers and from literature to benchmark suitable materials and device performance and lifetime, along with the literature and previous designs. The main output of the WP2 is the four deliverables (regarding sustainability & Life cycle assessment, process and quality requirements, market and strategic orientations and integration requirements) that will be shared within the consortium. Additionally, the general use-case description will be made public through the project website to describe the activities of the project to the public (Table 6).

Data Description	Data Origin / Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
Use-case description	Partners	.html	Public	N/A
Suppliers and literature material	Literature	.html, .pdf	Project Consortium	N/A
Deliverables	Partners	.docx, .pdf	Project Consortium	N/A

Meetings Minutes & Presentations	Partners	.docx, .pdf, .ppt	Project Consortium	N/A
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Table 6: LaserWay WP2 Data Mapping

3.3 WP3 WayFASTER – Machines with high dynamics for productivity increment

Regarding WP3, the objective of this work package is to develop innovative hardware and software solutions for laser machines that are specifically tailored for extremely high-speed laser applications. The main input is the data provided by WP2 related to the requirements for each project application and the existing literature and previous expertise on machine control and dynamics, high speed process control techniques and software solutions according to the mentioned specifications. The output will be the concept design of machine elements to be developed along the project, the definition of advance control strategies and the development of dedicated software solutions to satisfy the established requirements (Table 7).

Data Description	Data Origin / Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
Requirements (WP2)	Partners	.docx, .pdf, .xlsx	Project Consortium	N/A
Literature	Literature	.html, .pdf	Project Consortium	N/A
Previous expertise	Partners	.html, .pdf	Confidential	N/A
Machine conceptual designs	Partners	.docx, .pdf, CAD, .Tiff, .Jpeg, .png, .xlsx, .vid	Project Consortium	N/A
High speed active control techniques design (filter implementation)	Partners	.docx, .pdf, CAD, .Tiff, .Jpeg, .png, .xlsx	Confidential	N/A
High speed active control techniques design (active/passive damping techniques)	Partners	.docx, .pdf, CAD, .Tiff, .Jpeg, .png, .xlsx	Confidential	N/A
Development of a physics-based machine digital twin for developed advance technique optimization (offline)	Partners	.docx, .pdf, CAD, .Tiff, .Jpeg, .png, .xlsx, .vid	Confidential	N/A

productivity optimization related data for high-speed laser machines)				
Deliverables	Partners	.docx, .pdf	Project Consortium	N/A
Meetings Minutes & Presentations	Partners	.docx, .pdf, .ppt	Project Consortium	N/A

Table 7: LaserWay WP3 Data Mapping

3.4 WP4 WayBETTER – improvement of photonics for quality increment at high speeds

The primary goal of this work package is to devise and implement photonics technology solutions that address the complex challenges inherent in high-speed laser processing, ensuring the accurate and timely distribution of photons on the workpiece, enhancing process reliability and part precision. In addition, this work package aims to create innovative monitoring systems for real-time assessment and classification of processing status, thus enabling better quality control and optimization. The main input for WP3 would be the requirements defined in WP2 as well as the data generated from literature and previous expertise in the field. The main output will be the data generated regarding the conceptual designs of new solutions focused on achieving the above mentioned goal: new laser head concept base on laser beam shaping to counteract holes ovalization caused by the high traverse speeds required for large productivities; a laser beam delivery control based on the implementation in the laser head of sensors non-affected by the process (cutting edge monitoring sensors); an integrated Z-axis for ultra -responsive gap control (distance between the laser nozzle and the part to be processed); the improvement of the of the laser head electronics for enhanced real time gap control; and the development of in-line quality control based on different kinds of sensors (pyrometer, CMOS camera, etc.) and signal processing techniques (Table 12).

Data Description	Data Origin / Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
Requirements (WP2)	Partners	.docx, .pdf, .xlsx	Project Consortium	N/A
Literature	Literature	.html, .pdf	Project Consortium	N/A
Previous expertise	Partners	.html, .pdf	Confidential	N/A
New laser head concept based on laser shaping for high-speed drilling compensation	Partners	.docx, .pdf, CAD	Research purpose	N/A

(micro-drilled hole dimension accuracy & shape assurance data at high speed microdrilling)		.Tiff, .Jpeg, .png, .xlsx, .vid, .mat		
Laser beam delivery control concept based on cutting edge sensors	Partners	.docx, .pdf, CAD, .Tiff, .Jpeg, .png, .xlsx	Confidential	N/A
Laser head concept with an integrated Z axis for ultra-responsive gap control (Gap control measurements & behaviour data)	Partners	.docx, .pdf, CAD, .Tiff, .Jpeg, .png, .xlsx, .raub, .log, .mat	Confidential	N/A
Enhanced laser head electronics for improved real time gap control	Partners	.docx, .pdf, CAD, .Tiff, .Jpeg, .png, .xlsx, .vid, .raub, .log	Confidential	N/A
New inline monitoring concepts based on different kind of sensors (including data for sensor testing) and signal processing techniques	Partners	.docx, .pdf, CAD, .Tiff, .Jpeg, .png, .xlsx, .vid	Confidential	N/A
Results of experimental testing of the boundaries of the existing laser processing technologies to accommodate to faster dynamics	Hardness test; Tribological test; Microscopy	.docx, .pdf, .csv, .jpg	Research purpose	Public
Deliverables	Partners	.docx, .pdf	Project Consortium	N/A
Meetings Minutes & Presentations	Partners	.docx, .pdf, .ppt	Project Consortium	N/A

Table 8: LaserWay WP4 Data Mapping

3.5 WP5 WaySTRONGER – Digital and sustainable integration of technologies for flexible production

The main objective of this WP is the integration and validation of the technology concepts developed in the frame of WP3 and WP4, so the main input for WP5 is the data generated and provided as a result of the previously mentioned WP3 and WP4 and also the requirements defined for integration process in WP2. The most relevant output in this case would be the data generated around the integration and validation of the following concepts : the optomechanical system concept developed for improved gap control, the in-line monitoring concept consisting in the integration of sensors and real-time process fingerprint techniques to monitor the laser manufacturing processes and the quality monitoring information concept from in-process sensors to avoid productivity losses due to process failures and quality reductions. Additionally, in the frame of WP5 a Life Cycle Assessment study will be performed (Table 9).

Data Description	Data Origin / Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
Requirements (WP2)	Partners	.docx, .pdf, .xlsx	Project Consortium	N/A
Gap control: Z-axis bandwidth	CNC Machine	.csv	Project Consortium	N/A
Gap control: sensor quality and bandwidth	Sensor	.csv, .mat	Project Consortium	N/A
Gap control: control laws and communications for high sampling frequency	Partners	.csv	Project Consortium	Only for involved partners
Enhanced laser head electronics for improved real time gap control	Partners	.docx, .pdf, CAD	Confidential	Only for involved partners
Cloud platform for sensor data storage for quality control (monitoring data generated for 100% micro-hole quality control in high-speed micro-drilling-diameters, burs and spacing-).	Sensorized Machine	.mdf, .pdf, .Tiff, .Jpeg, .png, .mat	Project Consortium	N/A

Develop and implement actions to improve the production line's resilience to process defects (data generated regarding process capability/ flexibility to adapt to different microdrilled hole diameters)	Partners	CNC and PLC internal signals; Images of microdrilled samples	Confidential	N/A
Lyfecycle Assessment	Partners	.docx, .pdf, .Tiff, .Jpeg, .png, .xlsx		
Deliverables	Partners	.docx, .pdf	Project Consortium	N/A
Meetings Minutes & Presentations	Partners	.docx, .pdf, .ppt	Project Consortium	N/A

Table 9: LaserWay WP5 Data Mapping

3.6 WP6 LaserWay – Demonstrations

This WP aims at demonstrating a successful integration of LaserWay project solutions dedicated to the different laser technologies and the corresponding validation, in terms of productivity and quality requirements, through four demonstrators. The main data input for this WP are the demonstrators requirements and the most relevant data output will be the data generated from the in-line process quality control and prototype behaviour during the demonstrators production and the data related to the validation of the demonstrators (Table 10).

Data Description	Data Origin / Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
Demonstrators requirements	Partners	.docx, .pdf, .xlsx	Project Consortium	N/A
Quality control and prototype behaviour data	Prototype	.mat, .csv, .xlsx	Project Consortium	N/A
Required data to perform demonstration activities(CNC programs, Nesting programs,...)	Partners	.lsr, .ldf, .mdf	Confidential	N/A
Prototype and demo validation	Partners	.docx, .pdf, .xlsx	Project Consortium	N/A

Deliverables	Partners	.docx, .pdf	Project Consortium	N/A
Meetings Minutes & Presentations	Partners	.docx, .pdf, .ppt	Project Consortium	N/A

Table 10: LaserWay WP6 Data Mapping

3.7 WP7 LaserWay – Exploit & Collab (1st period)

The objective of this WP is to maximize the impact of the project results in the European industry and academic level by implementing the first steps of the Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Intellectual Property Protection Plan. Also in this work package, a business plan and exploitation activities will be performed. The main data input would be the existing expertise from partners to be protected and the expected knowledge and results to be disseminated, exploited and protected. The outcome would be a definition of strategies for both the communication and dissemination of the generated knowledge, and the commercialization of project’s results along with IP protection activities and recommendations for policies Table 11.

Data Description	Data Origin / Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
Existing expertise	Partners	.docx, .pdf	Confidential	N/A
Expected Knowledge and results to be generated	Prototype	.docx, .pdf, .xlsx	Project Consortium	N/A
Deliverables	Partners	.docx, .pdf	Project Consortium	N/A
Meetings Minutes & Presentations	Partners	.docx, .pdf, .ppt	Project Consortium	N/A
Posters, flyers	Custom made for Laserway	.pdf	Public	Design agreed by Project consortium
Website, Social media	LinkedIn, Twitter, Web	Public	Design agreed by Project consortium	Contents agreed with involved partners
Photo, video images,	Retrieved during physical or virtual	.jpg, .png, .asf, .avi, .mpeg	Public	Explicit consent received from appearing participants, Lawful

	project events			use-rights granted from media owners
Questionnaires, reports	Custom made for Laserway	.docx	Public	Contributors details either anonymised or simply consolidated
Presentations (workshops, conferences...)	Custom made for Laserway	.pdf, .pptx	Laserway template needs to be used.	Laserway template needs to be used. Contents agreed with involved partners. Acknowledgements to EU funding is compulsory
Scientific publications	LaserWay outputs	.pdf	Public	Access Contents agreed with involved partners. Acknowledgements to EU funding is compulsory

Table 11: LaserWay WP7 Data Mapping

3.8 WP8 LaserWay – Exploit & Collab (2nd period)

The objective of WP8 is to continue the work of the previous WP until the end of the project while maximizing sustainability and drafting guidelines to keep momentum between the partners beyond the end of the project. Therefore, the main data input is the output from WP7 and the knowledge and results generated in the second period of the project, and the main data output will be the final versions of the large scale dissemination and communication activities and the business cases and exploitation plan (Table 12).

Data Description	Data Origin / Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
WP7 output data	Partners	.docx, .pdf	Consortium	N/A
Knowledge and results generated (2^o period)	Partners	.docx, .pdf	Project Consortium	N/A
Deliverables	Partners	.docx, .pdf	Project Consortium	N/A
Meetings Minutes & Presentations	Partners	.docx, .pdf, .ppt	Project Consortium	N/A

Posters, flyers	Custom made for Laserway	.pdf	Public	Design agreed by Project consortium
Website, social media	LinkedIn, Twitter, Web	Public	Design agreed by Project consortium	Contents agreed with involved partners
Photo, images, video	Retrieved during physical or virtual project events	.jpg, .png, .asf, .avi, .mpeg	Public	Explicit consent received from appearing participants, Lawful use-rights granted from media owners
Questionnaires, reports	Custom made for Laserway	.docx	Public	Contributors details either anonymised or simply consolidated
Presentations (workshops, conferences...)	Custom made for Laserway	.pdf .pptx	Laserway template needs to be used.	Laserway template needs to be used. Contents agreed with involved partners. Acknowledgements to EU funding is compulsory
Scientific publications	LaserWay outputs	.pdf	Public	Access Contents agreed with involved partners. Acknowledgements to EU funding is compulsory

Table 12: LaserWay WP8 Data Mapping

4 FAIR data Management & ORPD

Zenodo is a trusted and widely used repository that is in line with LaserWay's goal of adhering to the FAIR principles. Additionally, it offers a user-friendly web interface enhancing the end-user experience. The way that Zenodo is designed to promote its credibility and address effectively the four elements of FAIR is thoroughly discussed below.

4.1 FAIR Data Management

4.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Data and metadata are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier. In particular, a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) is issued to every published record on Zenodo.
- Data are described by metadata that are compliant with DataCite's Metadata Schema minimum and recommended terms, with a few additional enrichments.
- Considering that the DOI is a top-level and a mandatory field in the metadata of each record, the metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe.
- Metadata of each record are indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing. They are also sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there.

4.1.2 Making data accessible

- Data-files may be deposited under closed, open, or embargoed access. Files deposited under closed access are protected against unauthorized access at all levels. In the case of the deposition of files under the embargo status, users provide an end-date for the embargo. The repository will restrict access to the data until the end of the embargo period; at which time, the content will become publicly available. Users may store restricted files with the ability to share access with others if certain requirements are met. These data will not be made publicly accessible, and sharing is only possible with the consent of the original depositor.
- Zenodo users must specify a license for all publicly available data. Licenses for closed access data may be specified in the associated description field.
- Record collections and metadata for individual records are harvestable using the OAI-MPH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata are also retrievable through the public REST-API.
- Both OAI-MPH and REST are open, free and universal protocols for information retrieval on the web.
- Metadata are publicly accessible and licensed under public domain (CC0), except for email addresses. Besides email addresses, no authorization is ever necessary to retrieve the rest of the metadata.
- Data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. Currently, this is the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which has an experimental program defined for the next 20 years at least. Nonetheless, a succession plan has been foreseen. In case of closure of the repository, efforts will be made to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.

4.1.3 Making data interoperable

- Zenodo uses JSON Schema as internal representation of metadata and offers export to other popular formats such as Dublin Core or MARCXML.
- For certain terms, it refers to open, external vocabularies, e.g.: license (Open Definition), funders (FundRef) and grants (OpenAIRE).
- Each referenced external metadata element is qualified by a resolvable URL.
- Zenodo supports all data file formats. To facilitate data interoperability, the project aims to store generated data under widely used formats and provide useful documentation (README files), where necessary.

4.1.4 Increase data re-use

- Each record contains a minimum of DataCite's mandatory terms, with optionally additional DataCite recommended terms and Zenodo's enrichments.
- License is one of the mandatory fields in Zenodo's metadata and is referring to an *Open Definition* license. Data downloaded by the users is subjected to the licenses specified in the metadata by the uploader.
- All data and metadata are traceable to a registered Zenodo user. Metadata can optionally describe the original authors of the published work.
- Zenodo is not a domain-specific repository. By complying with DataCite's Metadata Schema, the metadata meet one of the broadest cross-domain standards available.
- Data files are versioned. Records are not versioned. The uploaded data are archived as a Submission Information Package. Derivatives of data files are generated, but original content is never modified. Records can be retracted from public view; however, the data files and records are preserved.

4.2 Contribution to the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP)

Open Access (see Figure 3) is about offering on-line access to scientific information, cost-free to the end-user and in a multiple-use fashion. In the context of research and innovation, 'scientific information' refers to peer-reviewed scientific research articles published in scholarly journals and research data (data underlying publications, curated data and/or raw data).

Figure 3: Open Access in H2020 projects

The ORD pilot aims to improve and maximize access to and re-use of research data generated by LaserWay and takes into account the need to balance openness and protection of scientific information, commercialization and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), privacy concerns, security as well as data management and preservation questions. The project, along with the publication of scientific publications, will deposit at the same time the publication of research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited publications ('underlying data'). Publication of data within LaserWay will be accomplished on a voluntary basis by the stakeholders, and in full alignment with the Intellectual Property (IP) and the patenting activities of LaserWay. It is recognized that some research data cannot be made open and the principle of “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” will be applied. Considering the above, LaserWay aims at contributing data to the ORDP. Data sets that are candidates for sharing will certainly have been inspected to make sure that:

- They are not confidential, that they do not include commercially sensitive or personal info according to GDPR
- That permission from the relevant stakeholders and/or data objects has been obtained.
- That sharing the data does not damage exploitation or IP protection prospects.

The project will create a public repository in ZENODO to deposit Open Data following the FAIR data principles to ensure findable, accessible, interoperable data and to increase their re-use. The next version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) will explicitly specify what data will be open, how it will be exploited or made accessible for verification and re-use, and how it will be curated and preserved. Accordingly, datasets will be reviewed by the Data Owners and must be approved before becoming candidates for contribution to the open research. These parties and the respective technical consortium partner(s) will then agree on the licensing (e.g. creative commons or public domain). Following in principle approval, LaserWay will then make the dataset available through the LaserWay user community and upload content to the

existing relevant and suitable open access repositories. Where data must be embargoed towards IP protection or exploitation, a timeline for its release will be provided. The approval of the availability of data in an open approach will need to be sent to the project coordinator from the actual Data Owners via email. For this, a consent that the data can be distributed outside the consortium must be included in the approval email to the project coordinator. The information gathered in Table 13 should be included.

Data Owner	Description of Data	Data filenames and version	Consent to publish data outside the LaserWay consortium
Who is the data owner	What the data include	Files name and depository position	[YES/NO]

Table 13: Open Data Ownerships

5 General Data Protection Policy (GDPR)

As of May 2018, the GDPR has been applicable in all Member States in the European Union, as well as in the countries in the European Economic Area (EEA). Data confidentiality is an overriding concern throughout the LaserWay project and beyond, as the LaserWay framework will continue to be used afterwards, thus LaserWay aims at being fully GDPR compliant. All data to be collected from stakeholders in the project will be done in accordance with applicable ethical standards and requirements in the respective countries of the data collection, as well will be processed and handled in a secure way and in line with applicable rules and regulations on privacy and data protection. Table 14 presents the data and personal information that is planned to be collected and stored throughout the project duration and beyond as well as their access, storage, purpose and retention details.

Personal Description²	Data	Acces³	Storage⁴	Purpose⁵	Duration⁶
Official Contact List of LaserWay contacts	Internal to LaserWay (project partners only)	to	Sharepoint (Teams)	Management, organizations contact points	31/12/2026
Meetings' related material (agendas, presentations, signature lists, minutes)	Internal to LaserWay (project partners only)	to	Sharepoint (Teams)	Knowledge sharing, dissemination and management reasons	31/12/2026
Workshops/Conferences and Training sessions	Internal to LaserWay (project partners only)	to	Sharepoint (Teams)	Large event dissemination	31/12/2026

Meetings Minutes & Presentations	Internal to LaserWay (project partners only)	Sharepoint (Teams)	LaserWay reporting and consolidation of financial reports	31/12/2026
Reporting (C forms)	Internal to LaserWay (project partners only)	Sharepoint (Teams)	Public	5 years after the project's end

² Overall data description.

³ Determines who has access to the particular data (internal, external to consortium).

⁴ Storage places of actual data.

⁵ Intended purpose of data and reasons for keeping.

⁶ Duration of stored data (until when they will be kept).

Table 14: Data and Personal Information from day-to-day activities

6 Conclusions

The present document describes thoroughly the Data Management Plan (DMP) contemplating the description in detail the data and the mechanisms and strategies to manage them in the frame of the LaserWay project. It contemplates the data that will be produced, processed or used within the LaserWay scope along with their main relevant characteristics (type, nature,..) involved in each of the LaserWay WPs, as well as their relationship with the project goals. Also, the means and procedures that are employed to ensure compliance with FAIR principles, as specified by the EC, are established. In the same way, the measures taken to support the need for data confidentiality are described. A full section of this report has been devoted to address the security of personal data in compliance with GDPR (regulation) that has been developed to harmonize data privacy legislations throughout Europe, and also protect as well as enable all EU citizens' data privacy, by improving the methods that companies throughout the area approach data privacy. This section also covers all practices that LaserWay will follow to abide by the above, along with consent forms and internal processes that LaserWay prepared to implement and use.

6.1 Deviations from the DoA

No deviation from the DoA (Description of Actions) related to the Data Management Plan (DMP) has resulted.

7 Bibliography

There are no sources in the current document.

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